

The dual role of inflammation and tertiary lymphoid structures in tumor progression and immunity: a literature review and our experience

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Abstract

In the last decade, the term tertiary lymphoid structures (TLSs) has gained significant attention and is used to describe ectopic lymphoid organs that exhibit characteristics similar to secondary lymphoid organs (SLOs) and form in response to chronic inflammation. TLSs are closely related to cancer development and might serve as a predictive factor for patient prognosis. The relationship between tumors and TLSs is complex due to the influence of tumor-derived cytokines on the expression of TLS-derived cytokines and vice versa. Many articles have addressed TLSs and their significance in various carcinomas, and this study focuses on improving comprehension of the intrinsic mechanisms by which TLSs impact patient prognosis. This work is supported by data from our previous study on TLSs in patients with urothelial carcinoma of the bladder. However, literature data on the presence of TLSs in different neoplastic diseases remain scarce.

Keywords

biomarker, immunohistochemistry, tertiary lymphoid structure, TLS, tumor immunity

Introduction

Inflammation is a natural protective response of the body aimed at neutralizing harmful agents and preventing their spread, as well as clearing away damaged or dead cells and

tissue (Chen et al. 2017). It is well established that a notable inflammatory response is frequently observed within and surrounding tumors (Grivennikov et al. 2010). Moreover, many tumors exhibit signs of chronic inflammation, primarily involving immune cells such as lymphocytes,

plasma cells, and macrophages, and in some cases, a granulomatous pattern can be observed. Mediators involved in chronic inflammation play diverse and complex roles in cancer progression. Inflammatory processes can both facilitate and hinder tumor development. On one side, inflammation may contribute to the onset of malignancy, promote tumor growth, support tissue invasion, and enhance metastatic potential (Pahwa et al. 2025). On the other hand, it can also activate immune mechanisms that help suppress tumor expansion. A growing body of research has focused on tertiary lymphoid structures (TLSs) and their potential roles in different types of cancer (Chen et al. 2025). However, despite increasing interest, the available data on the presence of TLSs in various tumor types—and their correlation with factors such as tumor invasiveness, staging, and overall patient prognosis—remain limited.

The interaction between tumors and TLSs is particularly intricate. Cytokines produced by tumors can influence cytokine production within TLSs, and vice versa, creating a dynamic feedback loop that shapes the tumor microenvironment (Chu et al. 2024; Aquino et al. 2025).

In this paper, we aim to share our experience in assessing TLSs in the context of inflammation and tumor progression, as well as to present the most relevant papers in the field.

Search strategy

We conducted a systematic literature search to investigate the dual role of inflammation and tertiary lymphoid structures (TLSs) in tumor progression and antitumor immunity. The search was performed across four electronic databases—PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Embase—covering all records up to June 2025. We used a comprehensive Boolean search strategy to combine relevant concepts: (“tertiary lymphoid structures” OR

“ectopic lymphoid tissue” OR “tertiary lymphoid organs”) AND (“inflammation” OR “inflammatory response”) AND (“tumor progression” OR “cancer progression” OR “neoplasia” OR “tumor development”) AND (“antitumor immunity” OR “immune response” OR “immune infiltration” OR “tumor immunity”). Where available, the search was supplemented using MeSH terms (e.g., “Neoplasms”[MeSH], “Lymphoid Tissue”[MeSH]), and the results were limited to English-language studies in human and relevant animal models.

All retrieved references were imported into reference management software for duplicate removal. Titles and abstracts were independently screened by two reviewers. Full texts of potentially relevant studies were then assessed against pre-established eligibility criteria:

- Inclusion criteria included original research or review articles exploring the biological, clinical, or therapeutic roles of TLSs and/or inflammation in cancer, as well as studies evaluating TLS structure, immune functions, or prognostic value in tumor contexts.
- Exclusion criteria included non-cancer-related TLS studies, conference abstracts without full data, editorials, and commentaries.

Discrepancies were resolved by consensus or consultation with a third reviewer. The study selection process followed PRISMA 2020 guidelines, and the workflow is presented in Fig. 1.

Current concept of TLS

Secondary lymphoid organs (SLOs) play a pivotal role in initiating adaptive immune responses. Their development is driven by genetically programmed mechanisms that occur during embryonic growth. Interestingly, a similar process, known as lymphoid neogenesis, can be triggered in

Figure 1. PRISMA flow chart of the search strategy.

other tissues under certain conditions, leading to the formation of TLSs (Heimroth et al. 2020; Zhao et al. 2024). These organized immune cell clusters within tumors significantly influence the immune system's response to cancer, and their analysis has opened new possibilities for cancer immunotherapy.

TLSs share many structural and functional features with lymph nodes that are essential for adaptive immunity (Pimenta et al. 2014; Zhao et al. 2024). Typically, TLSs contain a T cell zone enriched with mature dendritic cells, a germinal center composed of follicular dendritic cells and proliferating B cells, and specialized blood vessels known as high endothelial venules (HEVs) (Narvaez et al. 2024) (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Histological similarities and structural differences between lymph nodes and TLSs.

Despite these similarities, important differences exist between lymph nodes and TLSs. Lymph nodes are encapsulated structures located at anatomically defined sites, whereas TLSs consist of non-encapsulated aggregates of immune and stromal cells that develop within tissues (Sato 2023). Furthermore, while SLOs arise during embryonic development through genetically predetermined pathways, TLSs form later in life in response to persistent inflammation or prolonged antigenic stimulation (Colbeck et al. 2017; Munoz-Erazo et al. 2020; Cui et al. 2025) (Table 1).

SLOs form in specific, anatomically consistent locations, whereas TLSs tend to appear transiently in non-lymphoid tissues and often regress once the antigenic stimulus is resolved. Nonetheless, because TLSs develop under conditions of chronic inflammation or cancer, they are capable of mimicking the functions of SLOs, particularly in regulating immune responses within tumors (Pimenta et al. 2014). TLSs contribute to both humoral and cell-mediated immunity. In humoral immune responses, B cells generate antibodies targeting specific antigens. In cell-mediated immunity, activated T cells attack infected or abnormal cells (Germain et al. 2015). Within TLSs—as in conventional SLOs—antigens are presented to both B and T lymphocytes, rendering TLSs highly effective in coordinating immune activity (Zhang et al. 2024).

Nevertheless, TLSs can vary in their level of maturity, depending on the presence of germinal centers and class-switched B cells. Their presence in tumors is often associated with increased infiltration of CD8+ T cells (Vion et al. 2025). Consequently, the presence of TLSs in epithelial tumors may play a crucial role in the host defense against cancer (Schumacher and Thommen 2022).

Although the prognostic value of TLSs remains under extensive investigation and definitive evidence is still lacking, their detection in target organs in autoimmune diseases has historically been associated with worsening clinical symptoms and adverse patient outcomes (Pipi et al. 2018). In contrast, the presence of TLSs in certain solid tumors has been associated with improved antitumor immune responses. Several reports have described situations in which tumor cells induce regulatory T cells while simultaneously suppressing host immune responses, thereby compromising antitumor immunity (Houel et al. 2023; Bao et al. 2024). However, antitumor immune responses are complex and proceed through multiple stages, and understanding these processes is essential for the development of effective immunotherapies. Moreover, the role of the immune system remains poorly defined in many tumor types (Su et al. 2025). Significant gaps therefore persist in our understanding of TLS biology. For example, the association between TLS density and patient survival is not consistently observed across different cancer types.

It is important to note that TLSs do not form during embryogenesis. Their development begins later in adulthood and is often associated with protective properties, such as the localized aggregation of lymphocytes within target organs after disease onset (Sato et al. 2023).

With regard to terminology, different sources in the literature use various terms to describe TLSs, including ectopic lymphoid systems and ectopic germinal centers. These terms emphasize the immunological significance of these lymphoid structures and should be applied only when the composition of the germinal center is histologically confirmed (Jones et al. 2016). The term tertiary lymphoid first appeared in the literature in 1992, when it was introduced by Louis Picker and Eugene Butcher (Picker and Butcher 1992). It was used to describe the formation of extranodal lymphoid structures in which lymphocytes or immune memory cell precursors can be restimulated by antigens, potentially leading to clonal expansion and TLS formation (Pipi et al. 2018). Organs such as the liver, heart, pancreas, synovium, and salivary glands are not embryologically predisposed to lymphoid tissue development. Therefore, lymphocyte aggregation within these tissues should be classified as TLSs (Barone et al. 2016).

TLSs form in response to sequential activation by proinflammatory cytokines and members of the tumor necrosis factor receptor family following local interactions between inflammatory immune cells and stromal cells. Fibroblasts, perivascular myofibroblasts, and mesenchymal cells participate in TLS development through multiple

Table 1. Comparative histology of lymph nodes and tertiary lymphoid structures (TLSs). Although lymph nodes and TLSs share key immunological features, including organized B and T cell zones and the presence of HEVs, structural differences—most notably the absence of a capsule in TLSs—reflect their distinct roles in immune surveillance and immune responses.

Feature	Lymph node	Tertiary lymphoid structure (TLS)
Capsule	Present; composed of dense connective tissue	Absent; lacks a defined capsule
Location	Situated along lymphatic vessels throughout the body	Formed in non-lymphoid tissues at sites of chronic inflammation and tumor
B cell zones	Well-defined follicles with germinal centers in the cortex	Present; may form germinal center-like structures
T cell zones	Paracortex region rich in T cells	Surround B cell areas; organization varies
High endothelial venules (HEVs)	Present; facilitate lymphocyte entry from blood	Present; support lymphocyte recruitment
Fibroblastic reticular cells (FRCs)	Form a network supporting T cell zones	Present; contribute to TLS structure
Function	Filter lymph; initiate adaptive immune responses	Elicit local immune responses in chronic inflammation and tumors

mechanisms (Picker and Butcher 1992; Papi et al. 2018). Some hypotheses propose that TLSs existed in ectopic tissues before the full development of secondary lymphoid organs (SLOs), serving to support SLO survival and maturation (Luther et al. 2002).

From a physiological perspective, the generation of a humoral immune response requires physical interactions between naive B cells and T cells within a confined, chemokine-rich microenvironment. Lymphocytes migrate from the bloodstream into secondary lymphoid organs in response to chemotactic gradients (Gulinac et al. 2020). Ligands and chemokine receptors regulate the recirculation of naive B cells through the internal region of the B cell follicle and the peripheral T–B cell border, thereby facilitating contact between B cells and antigen-activated T cells. Following antigen encounter, B cells migrate within follicles to the dark zone of germinal centers, a highly hypoxic region. There, centroblasts undergo rapid proliferation and upregulate activation-induced cytidine deaminase, leading to single-base pair substitutions in immunoglobulin gene segments within the variable region. This process is known as somatic hypermutation (Colbeck et al. 2017).

It is also important to recognize that TLSs do not develop in all patients, even within the same tissue type. This variability is reflected in differences in organizational features, suggesting a gradient related to antigen load or inflammatory intensity that supports TLS establishment (Asam et al. 2021). The precise triggers underlying TLS formation in specific patients remain unclear, and biomarkers predicting the development of tertiary lymphoid structures are still under investigation. One contributing factor may be the limited need for biopsy examination, particularly in patients with inflammatory bladder diseases, which are often identified through laboratory testing alone. Current evidence largely supports the hypothesis that TLS formation results from persistent inflammation or sustained antigenic stimulation (Hjelmström et al. 2000).

The fundamental research, conducted by Nancy Ruddle's group, suggests that chronic inflammation is the “driving force” in the process of TLS formation (Kratz et al. 1996; Ruddle 1999). TLSs have been found in the liver and stomach of mice and humans infected with *H. pylori*.

In this specific environment, the integrity of TLSs is disrupted by the implementation of antibiotics and the subsequent reduction in bacterial load (Wotherspoon et al. 1994; Bery et al. 2022).

These findings suggest that antigens and the recognition of pathogen- or damage-associated molecular patterns by immune cells play a critical role in the formation and organization of TLSs. Additionally, reducing the local antigenic load can compromise their integrity. While lymphokines and homeostatic chemokines are thought to be essential for the formation and organization of TLSs, several studies have highlighted the contribution of additional pro-inflammatory cytokines to their formation (Rangel-Moreno et al. 2011; Botelho et al. 2013).

Materials and methods

We examined two cases of low-grade (LG) non-invasive urothelial carcinoma from the tissue database of Grand Hospital de l'Estre Francilien, Jossigny, France.

Tissue collection and histopathological assessment

Formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) bladder tumor specimens were obtained from patients undergoing transurethral resection of bladder tumor (TURBT). All samples were collected as part of routine diagnostic procedures. Histopathological evaluation and grading were performed by certified pathologists (authors MG and DD) according to WHO classification and TNM staging, where applicable.

Histology and immunohistochemistry

Histological analysis of the tissues was performed using the automatic tissue processor “DIAPATH EN ISO 9001:2000,” and 4–5 μm formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded tissue sections underwent routine staining with hematoxylin–eosin (HE) to determine the presence of TLSs. Immunohistochemistry was performed following standard protocols. Appropriate positive and negative controls were included.

To identify and evaluate TLSs, pathologists typically start with standard hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining and then apply immunohistochemistry using markers such as CD31, CD34, CD10, CD23, CD3, CD20, CD4, CD8, CD68, S100, C-kit, smooth muscle actin, desmin, vimentin, podoplanin, Ki67, ckAE1/AE3, IgG4, and PDL1.

Results

It is important to note that recognizing TLSs in biopsy samples, classifying them, and understanding their role in anticancer immunity depend in part on the size of the tissue sample. Larger surgical specimens are more likely to reveal the full spectrum of these structures.

In the examined bladder tumor specimens, mature TLS type 3/grade 3 was identified within the tumor-associated stroma of low-grade (LG), non-invasive urothelial carcinoma. At low magnification, the TLSs appeared as well-demarcated lymphoid aggregates located in the stromal compartment adjacent to the tumor tissue (Fig. 3). A higher-power view confirmed the presence of a dense and organized lymphoid architecture, consistent with a mature TLS (Fig. 4).

Figure 3. TLS of type 3 (grade 3) in the stroma of LG non-invasive papillary urothelial carcinoma of the bladder, HE, $\times 50$.

Figure 4. TLS of type 3 (grade 3) in the stroma of LG non-invasive urothelial carcinoma, HE, $\times 200$ and HE, $\times 50$.

Discussion

Our previous studies (Gulinac et al. 2020) have shown that not only the existence of TLS in the tumor microenvironment is important, but also their precise localization, such as intratumoral TLS, which are most often an indicator of a favorable prognosis, especially in patients with pancreatic cancer. Similarly, peritumoral TLS correlates with better protective immunity and improved prognosis in patients with hepatocellular carcinoma. Despite these mixed findings from studies on TLS in tumors of varying histogenesis, the accuracy of this information is often dependent on the size of the biopsy samples analyzed. Larger biopsy tissues provide more accurate morphological information and are of great importance for patient prognosis.

According to the literature data and our observations, we suggest that TLS in all tumors may represent a promising histological feature for maximizing therapeutic strategies with checkpoint inhibitors and improving clinical outcomes for patients. They appear likely to be part of an adaptive immune response. They may help diagnose and understand the immunobiology of many tumors and could also guide patient selection for immunotherapy because tumor-associated TLS are essential modulators of the cancer immunologic microenvironment.

When a neoplastic disease is present, one of the protective mechanisms exhibited by TLS is the local aggregation of lymphocytes, which represents a significant component of antitumor immunity. However, histological confirmation is necessary to further clarify this process (Jones et al. 2016).

The thymus and bone marrow are the primary lymphoid organs where immune cell formation occurs. Secondary lymphoid organs (SLOs), such as lymph nodes, tonsils, the spleen, and mucous membranes, participate in preprogrammed adaptive immunity to eradicate infections and harmful agents. These organs are the sites where interactions between antigen-specific naive lymphocytes and antigen-presenting cells occur and display distinctive features, such as encapsulation, specific anatomical location, and preprogrammed embryo- and ontogenesis (Colbeck et al. 2017). Tertiary lymphoid structures largely resemble lymph node architecture. However, several key differences exist. First, TLS are not genetically programmed and do not form during embryonic stages. Second, TLS are aggregates of immune and stromal cells without encapsulation. Third, TLS forms in response to local chronic inflammation and neoplastic transformation. Finally, TLS forms temporarily in non-lymphoid organs. For this reason, lymphocyte aggregation in organs such as the liver, heart, pancreas, synovium, or salivary glands should be defined as TLS, as these organs are not embryologically predisposed to lymphoid tissue development (Barone et al. 2016; Colbeck et al. 2017).

TLS are formed in response to a series of interactions between proinflammatory cytokines and members of the TNF receptor family at sites of local chronic inflammation following cross-reactions between inflammatory

immune cells and stromal cells. Consequently, they function primarily to potentiate local immune responses at their sites of formation, similarly to SLOs. The main cytokines involved in cellular regulation include IL-13, IL-17, and IL-22 (Pipi et al. 2018; Zhang et al. 2024; Li et al. 2025). This results in local fibroblast proliferation and expression of lymphoid stromal chemokines, such as CXCL13, CCL19, and CCL21, leading to structural organization of lymphoid tissue and active involvement of B cells, T cells, and dendritic cells through receptor expression, respectively. Hence, TLSs possess the ability to exert control over or aggravate certain diseases. This process depends on the nature and histological configuration of the neoplastic disease (Picker and Butcher 1992; Colbeck et al. 2017; Pipi et al. 2018).

To the best of our knowledge, TLS do not develop in all patients, even within the same tissue type, as demonstrated by the identification of diverse organizational characteristics, suggesting a potential gradient in the quantity-to-quality ratio of presented antigens or the intensity of the inflammatory response that supports their formation. The specific triggers underlying TLS formation in certain individuals remain unclear, and research continues to identify biomarkers capable of predicting tertiary lymphoid structure development. We believe that one contributing factor is the infrequency of biopsy examinations, particularly in patients with inflammatory bladder conditions, which are often detected through laboratory testing. Available evidence strongly supports the concept that TLS formation is driven primarily by persistent inflammation or continuous antigenic stimulation (Hjelmström et al. 2000).

The essential study conducted by Nancy Ruddle's group (1999) indicates that persistent inflammation acts as the primary catalyst in TLS development. These findings further suggest that antigens and the recognition of pathogen- or damage-associated molecular patterns by immune cells play a critical role in lymphoid neogenesis. Additionally, reduction of the local antigenic load can compromise TLS integrity. While lymphokines and homeostatic chemokines are considered essential for TLS formation and organization, several studies have highlighted the contribution of additional pro-inflammatory cytokines to this process (Vion et al. 2025).

The inflammatory origin of extranodal lymphoid structures can be further illustrated by inducible bronchus-associated lymphoid tissue (iBALT), a lymphoid tissue in the lungs associated with pulmonary inflammation or infection. In humans, iBALT is linked not only to pulmonary infections but also to rheumatoid arthritis, tuberculosis, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Chronic exposure to antigens or cigarette smoke, particularly in COPD, induces lymphoid neogenesis (Rangel-Moreno et al. 2011; Botelho et al. 2013).

According to available data, both the presence of TLS in the tumor microenvironment and their specific localization are crucial. Intratumoral TLS are frequently associated with improved prognosis, particularly in patients with

pancreatic cancer (Su et al. 2025). Likewise, peritumoral TLS has been linked to enhanced protective immunity in hepatocellular carcinoma. Despite variable findings across studies involving tumors of different histogenetic origins, the reliability of these observations depends largely on biopsy sample size.

Larger biopsy specimens provide clearer morphological detail and enable more accurate TLS classification, which is critical for patient prognosis and treatment planning. Standard hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining, followed by immunohistochemistry using markers such as CD31, CD34, CD10, CD23, CD3, CD20, CD4, CD8, CD68, S100, C-kit, smooth muscle actin, desmin, vimentin, podoplanin, Ki67, ckAE1/AE3, IgG4, and PDL1, is routinely employed.

Conclusion

In summary, factors regulating TLS formation in epithelial tissues, such as chemokines and cytokines, most likely also contribute to an antitumor immune response in several carcinomas. What remains to be clearly elucidated is whether the tumor cell itself is responsible for the expression of factors that stimulate TLS formation and how immunotherapy treatment, either alone or in conjunction with current chemotherapy, can be used to manipulate the tumor immune environment to reactivate an antitumor response. Importantly, TLS assessment can be performed using routine histopathological evaluation, including H&E staining, making it feasible for clinical implementation. Overall, TLSs represent a promising biomarker that may support prognostic stratification and potentially inform therapeutic decision-making, although further studies are needed to standardize evaluation methods and validate their predictive value across tumor types.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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